

How post-factualism creates new needs for the epistemology of mathematics

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Discussions in mathematics education research have lately turned towards the phenomenon of post-factual discourses and reflected on the role of mathematics education in facing this challenge. While contributions so far have focussed on fact checking, source criticism, and a critical attitude towards mathematical models, this essay establishes that such scepticism lies at the very heart of post-factualism, and that its use in education bears the danger of producing and fortifying post-factual attitudes instead of overcoming them. It is shown that instead we require to acknowledge the roots of such scepticism in relativist epistemologies and to find answers to the question how facts are possible if all knowledge is relative. This essay refers to Hacking's framework of styles of reasoning as a possible solution to this dilemma.

Why bother?

The growing impact of post-factual discourses and the declining trust in science indicate that the rational society and liberal democracy are facing a crisis. Mathematics education, which may be regarded as part of an appropriate strategy to address post-factualism, might just as well bear responsibility in producing anti-rationalist sentiments, presuming it failed to introduce a wide selection of students to rational argumentation, and instead promoted dependence on teachers as authorities of knowledge, the uncritical processing of pre-determined rules, and an unjustified trust in the omnipotence of mathematical solutions in real-world applications. This alarming possibility should direct our attention at the epistemological question how mathematics is effective in creating factuality.

In the next section, I will discuss how post-factual attitudes have been approached in mathematics education research so far. After that, a closer look at post-factual attitudes and at epistemology more generally will recontextualise the above problem in a field of more general epistemological problems: Following the argument that it is unreasonable to conceive of truth and factuality as an attribute that is independent from humans, and embracing the relativist assumption that truth and factuality are products of human understanding, the urging question will be how truth and factuality can be conceptualised in the first place. I will end this essay with a brief outlook on a possible solution and its implications for mathematics education research.

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Mathematics education research on post-factualism

Published discussions on post-factual discourses are scarce in mathematics education. I searched the lists of contents and, if accessible in digital form, the whole text corpus of the articles published in eleven different Anglophone and six different Germanophone mathematics education journals for articles containing the terms ‘fake news’, ‘post-factual’, ‘postfactual’ or ‘post-truth’, or their German equivalents.¹ The search yielded five results (Heitwerth, 2020; Oldenburg, 2020; Orey & Rosa, 2018; Pais, 2018; Trakulphadetkrai, 2018), but in all cases post-factualism is only addressed causally. A search for these terms in connection with ‘mathematics education’ on Google and Google Scholar yielded three more results (Hauge, 2019; Hauge et al., 2019; Marcone et al., 2019), which feature post-factualism as a main theme. I will not discuss Pais’s (2018) summary of Borovik’s (2017) concern about the diffusion of fake news through automated big-data processing, nor will I address Trakulphadetkrai’s (2018) report that two plenary speakers at the 9th British Congress of Mathematics Education reminded the participants ‘that data needed to be interpreted with care, particularly in the age of fake news’ (p. 50). The former is not of central importance for the question discussed in this essay, while the brevity of the latter makes it difficult to interpret the statement.

In their discussion of a mathematical modelling course in a virtual learning environment (VLE), Orey and Rosa (2018) argued:

This particular form of pedagogical action on the VLE web site directed students towards the development of sound arguments based on data that they collected and towards observing, generalizing, and applying mathematical models to solve future problems faced by their own communities. Also, in a context where information is often unreliable, it helps individuals to move away from emotional manipulation (via social media and *fake news*) and to learn to search for deeper explanations and distinct ways of reflecting and dealing with societal issues based on the scientific method and factual data. (p. 183, original emphasis)

Heitwerth (2020) reflected on mathematical models that were used in public communication in Germany to legitimise the social lockdown during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in 2020. He argued that such reflections are necessary so that students can detect ‘fake news’ about the corona crisis and understand the importance of ‘evidence-based politics’: ‘Following this idea, a pro-scientific perspective can be supported, so that the individual epistemic beliefs of the learners may be based on facts and not fakes’ (p. 199, my translation). Heitwerth discussed how an understanding of graphs of functions, in this case relating time to the number of registered SARS-CoV-2 infections, can help to evaluate the

¹ The Anglophone journals were Canadian Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education, Educational Studies in Mathematics, For the Learning of Mathematics, International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education, Journal for Research in Mathematics Education, Mathematics in School, Mathematics Teaching, Mathematics Teaching in Middle School, Research in Mathematics Education and ZDM Mathematics Education. The Germanophone journals were Der Mathematikunterricht, Journal für Mathematik-Didaktik, Mathematica Didactica, Mathematik Lehren, Mitteilungen der Gesellschaft für Didaktik der Mathematik and MNU-Journal.

legitimacy of graphs shown in media and the claims that can follow from their interpretation. Both studies illustrate how mathematics can be used to question the epistemic status of claims and to legitimise claims mathematically. Thereby, they suggest that an awareness of this role of mathematics is suitable to counter post-factual discourses. In both cases, the activities question the legitimacy of mathematical representations (numbers and graphs) which are derived from modelling activities. However, it remains opaque what 'the scientific method', 'factual data' or 'facts' might mean and in which way mathematics can contribute or not to reaching this standard. This leads to the epistemological question how mathematics is effective in establishing or refuting the fact status of claims.

The most elaborated work on post-factualism in mathematics education was developed by Hauge and colleagues. Her approach is more specific as it focusses on the role of mathematics in manipulation through fake news. Hauge (2019) discussed problems one faces when discussing the trustworthiness of numbers in news in mathematics education, including the difficulty of distinguishing uncertain, wrong or deceptive uses of mathematics, the arbitrariness of the social production of numbers in applications of mathematics, and the declining trust in science. Hauge et al. (2019) argued that '[s]uch situations require a critical investigation of data, simplifications, assumptions, graphic presentations, validity of conclusions and how limitations in mathematics-based argumentation can be linked to an underlying agenda' (p. 3). The breadth of these requirements indicates that epistemological awareness is required on top of mathematical knowledge. Based on her contemplations, Hauge (2019) suggested among other things that students should learn mathematical concepts, how to argue based on applications of mathematics, how argumentation is structured in general, and that mathematical methods are neither correct nor incorrect but arbitrary.

Hauge et al. (2019) discussed an example of fake news, where the choice of statistical data and a not fully justified application of mathematical concepts resulted in politically biased statements. This discussion, just as the studies by Heitwerth (2020) and Orey and Rosa (2018), faced applications of mathematics on an exemplary basis. Considering aspects of mathematics such as deductive proof, it appears necessary to expand the focus beyond mathematical modelling when evaluating how mathematics is productive in establishing facts. The merely exemplary character of the present discussions suggests that there is a lack of solid epistemological theory of how mathematics establishes facts.

The two remaining publications indeed turn towards epistemological problems, although in a very fundamental way. In his critique of the assumption held in radical constructivism that truth is relative, Oldenburg (2020) argued that

an enlightened pedagogy must take a clear stand against such views. But it will not succeed in doing so if it relies on constructivism, which encourages such relativism and considers 'alternative facts', as the current US president [Donald Trump] likes to use them, to be perfectly normal. (p. 80, my translation)

The concern that post-modern tendencies in mathematics education may go hand-in-hand or even brisk up post-factual attitudes is shared by Marcone et al. (2019). The authors

referred to the increasing impact of fake news and asked how to relate to that problem in mathematics education. They suggested that the ‘timeless reasoning of mathematics’ is losing relevance as discourses become more ‘appealing of the emotional side’ (p. 186). Reflecting on the role of mathematics education research, they wrote:

It is paradoxical that critical scholars have fought against the uncritical faith in mathematics and now the problem is that there is a uncritical suspicion in mathematics. We wonder if the Mathematics Education community played some part in this battle. Part of the Mathematics Education community always criticizes the ideology of certainty, but now that it is gone from some places, some of us are afraid. Now the dominant discourse is to bypass and ignore scientific facts. (pp. 186–187)

Marcone et al. (2019) concluded:

Our contention is that we are not being successful at promoting a critical distance towards mathematics, and that many of our arguments against universality and neutrality have been trivialized and turned back against its original intention. [...] We need to understand and operate within this mechanism of de-mathematising public discussion. We need to begin to spin in a different direction to rescue the critical perspective on mathematics. (p. 187)

For that purpose, this essay will look further into the phenomenon of post-factual discourses, before it will face the problem how an epistemology of mathematics could conceptualise truth without falling back into essentialism.

From post-structuralism to post-factualism

MacMullen (2020) asked ‘what would it mean for discourses to be post-factual’ (p. 97), only that he, working in political science, wrote ‘politics’ where I now write ‘discourses’. He differentiated four ideal types of post-factual attitudes. This distinction will prove essential for my line of argument.

The first attitude is *unconscious* post-factualism. Here, someone is not even aware of her involvement in post-factual discourses. MacMullen (2020) highlighted that psychological mechanisms facilitate the acceptance of post-factual information. Irrespective of the factual status of a claim, we are more likely to accept it as true if it fits our values and our personal experience, if we hear it oftentimes, and if we trust the people holding it. Needless to say that many professional political campaigners have specialised in using such psychological mechanisms for the benefit of their party. These effects are further supported by the tendency of digital social networking to connect people with similar mindsets and not people with conflicting mindsets. People with unconscious post-factual attitudes might usually prefer factual discourses and might find it disturbing to realise that they have participated in post-factual discourses. An obvious educative approach to this attitude would be to teach people to be sceptical about truth claims and to question the interests and values that lie behind them. This appears to be the position of the studies in mathematics education discussed above, especially that of Hauge (2019), whose focus on fake news led her to assume a dichotomy between ruthless, interest-driven producers and passive, helpless victims of post-factual discourses. In contrast we should also consider in how far post-factual

discourses are actively produced and shared by a wide range of people, often with awareness of their problematic epistemic status, as in the following three attitudes.

The second attitude is *metaphysical* post-factualism. Here, post-modern critique of truth and objectivity is used to argue that truth and objectivity are nothing but interest-driven constructions, which blurs the distinction between factual and post-factual claims altogether. MacMullen (2020) remarked that this attitude is a rare intellectual variety of post-factualism. Nevertheless, this attitude highlights central epistemological problems, which I will address later in this essay.

The third attitude is *motivational* post-factualism. Here, not denying the existence of facts, people choose to rather trust in a discourse that ‘expresses their values and makes them feel good, often by providing affirmation, a sense of community and identity, and perhaps some degree of entertainment’ (MacMullen, 2020, p. 105). They acknowledge the problematic epistemic status of post-factual claims but refuse the effort that it would take to evaluate such claims and to counter the psychological mechanisms that lead people to unconscious post-factualism. They widely dismiss concerns for the effects of their reliance on post-factual information. An obvious educative approach to this attitude would be to raise awareness for the individual and societal effects of this epistemological idleness. Reflections on the effects of the reliance on post-factual claims on the policy making of some countries during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in 2020 might already teach such a lesson.

The fourth attitude is *epistemic* post-factualism, whose impact MacMullen (2020) held to be underestimated. Here, not denying the existence of facts, someone assumes to lack the skills or resources to evaluate claims but does not trust experts either: ‘Seeing no way to be guided by the facts, such epistemically post-factual citizens consciously make their political decisions in a different way’ (p. 109). MacMullen established that there is no one-dimensional approach to post-factualism, for the educative approach recommended for unconscious post-factualism, that is being sceptical of truth claims and questioning the interests and values they are based on, appear only to solidify the attitude of epistemic post-factualism. Instead, he argued that these people ‘need a better understanding of how communities of experts and legitimate news organizations operate and the associated (defeasible) reasons to trust their empirical claims’ (p. 116).

It becomes clear that it is insufficient and might be counter-productive to face post-factual discourses merely by establishing their post-factual status and by learning to question the interests and values of the participants in this discourse as done in the examples from mathematics education presented by Hauge et al. (2019), Heitwerth (2020), and Orey and Rosa (2018). People with attitudes of conscious post-factualism do not see the post-factual status of claims as a problem and already mistrust the representatives of factual claims. Considering the metaphysical, motivational and epistemic types of conscious post-factualism, what is needed to rebuild trust in factual discourses is an epistemological legitimisation that factual discourses are possible, that it is worth the effort to prefer facts over sentiment, and that laypersons have the ability to judge whether a claim is based on facts or not. Thus, the scene is set for the discussion of genuinely epistemological questions

in the mathematics classroom – at least if mathematics education is supposed to play a part in addressing post-factual attitudes.

Epistemological education in the mathematics classroom

Oldenburg (2020) hoped for a new kind of realism to rescue the idea of truth and insight which he saw represented in mathematics. Chakravartty (2017) proposed to call an epistemology ‘realist’ if it follows

- the metaphysical assumption that the objects of reality exist independently of human beings,
- the linguistic assumption that language allows for a true description of reality, and
- the epistemological assumption that knowledge resembles reality.

Especially mathematicians are said to often share realist positions (Davis & Hersh, 1980). This becomes obvious when we presume that the law of the excluded middle (assuming that a claim is true or false and not beyond or in between that) is an uncircumventable law of thought for any sane person, or that the decimal expansion of π , defined as the ratio of a circle’s circumference to its diameter, stays the same anywhere, at any time, for anybody, also for aliens whom we send this decimal expansion to illustrate the intellectual achievements of us Earthlings.

However, closer analysis reveals some fundamental problems of realism. Although some of these problems were already debated in ancient anti-Eleatic philosophy and re-entered the philosophical stage in the eighteenth century by philosophers such as Berkeley, Hume and Kant (Liston, 2020), they were hardly taken into account in the wider field of science and arts until the emergence of post-modern and constructivist paradigms in the second half of the twentieth century. The following line of argument is an abridged selection from a philosophical discussion which easily fill books (e.g., Audi, 1997/2010; Landesman, 1997):

- Epistemologically, it has been established that we, limited by our sensual perceptions, cannot know in how far our theories accurately resemble an independent existence or if they leave blind spots (e.g., from a biological perspective, Maturana & Varela, 1984). The epistemological assumption had been called into question from within mathematics as the discovery of non-Euclidean geometries raised serious doubts whether geometric theories were indeed simply representations of an independent world (Davis & Hersh, 1980).
- Metaphysically, this means that neither can we determine if a world independent of human beings exists, nor does it matter epistemologically. The metaphysical assumption is therefore scientifically undecidable and reduced to a matter of belief. Yet, Horkheimer and Adorno (2002) noted that a belief in truths independent of humans can be frightening and dangerous, for it degrades the role of humans from active and ethically responsible constructors of their intellectual world to passive discoverers of already decided facts (p. 8).

- Linguistically, post-structuralist studies suggest that academic discourses, for example on insanity, delinquency, sexuality and truth itself, cannot be understood as a true description of reality, but constitute a historically contingent product which depends on values, interests and power relations (e.g., Foucault, 1961). Elsewhere, I presented such a post-structuralist argumentation for logical thinking (Kollosche, 2014b, or, if you can read German, preferably Kollosche, 2014a, Ch. 5). The ineluctable discrepancy between discourses and that which escapes articulation constitutes a central pillar of Lacan's psychoanalysis (Žižek, 1994). Subsequent studies following the post-structural paradigm have focussed on a deconstruction of ever more hegemonic discourses. This included changing perspectives on mathematics, which has come to be understood as an at least partly arbitrary product of history and social struggle (Davis & Hersh, 1980), as a weapon of colonising non-Western epistemologies (D'Ambrósio, 2007) and as a gender-biased style of thinking (Burton, 1995).

I referred to Marcone et al.'s (2019) and Oldenburg's (2020) fear that the growing acceptance of post-factual discourses coincided or has even been nourished by the refutation of realism and the orientation towards relativist epistemologies. Baghramian and Carter (2019) explain relativism as 'the view that truth and falsity, right and wrong, standards of reasoning, and procedures of justification are products of differing conventions and frameworks of assessment and that their authority is confined to the context giving rise to them', which would include constructivist and post-structural positions. Relativist epistemologies do not face the fundamental problems of realism discussed above, but, as Koschorke (2019) pointed out, they face the problem that they do not explain what should be regarded as truth, as there is no human-independent authority left to judge the suitability of any discourse for producing facts.

At least in the case of post-structuralism, this theoretical limitation has to be understood historically. Post-structuralism developed in a Europe reflecting on the horrors of the Second World War and experiencing the process of political decolonisation. Left protest movements were concerned with challenging authorities, refusing hegemonic world views, opening the public discourse for marginalised positions and advocating for a pluralism of lifestyles. The objective was to counter hegemonic discourses and to create spaces for alternative positions, not to (re)establish a basis for intellectual consensus.

Koschorke (2019) and MacMullen (2020) supported Marcone et al.'s (2019) and Oldenburg's (2020) fear that relativism has prepared the stage for post-factualism. McIntyre (2018) documented in great detail how political and economic agents learned to deploy post-structural lines of argumentation in order to change the rules of a debate to their advantage. Thus, relativist positions have become common among non-researchers, including the assumptions that truth is relative to arbitrary frameworks of reference, that experts are biased and therefore untrustable, and that truth claims are mere deceptions waiting to be

deconstructed. This is how the refutation of essentialism has facilitated the conscious acceptance of post-factual attitudes.

Koschorke (2019) and MacMullen (2020) assumed that the awareness of epistemological problems in the wider public cannot easily be erased in order to return to factual public discourses. This calls for more elaborated answers on how a consensus on knowledge can be achieved in contemporary societies. However, Koschorke (2015) demonstrated that contemporary attempts to establish a new form of realism do not solve but merely ignore the fundamental problems of realism. As of now, there appears to be no epistemological position which could reinstate the above-mentioned assumptions of realism while overcoming the problems they invoke. Any epistemological solution will therefore have to be sensitive to anti-essentialist arguments. Just like Koschorke (2019) argued for cultural studies, we face the open question how we can find our way

out of the dead zone into which the discipline has maneuvered itself, following decades of deessentialization, doubt about norms, and institutional critique—without giving up the emancipatory potential and cognitive achievements of poststructuralist theories and their global advancement. (p. 1156)

Styles of reasoning: A solution!?

Elsewhere, I discuss Ian Hacking's epistemological framework as a possible solution (Kollosche, 2021). Here, I can only sketch the basic idea of the framework: Based on the study of the historical development of styles of scientific thinking by Crombie (1994), Hacking (1982) proposed that different styles of reasoning define which statements are candidates for truth-or-falsity, how their truth value can be determined, and what the objects of their statements mean. For example, the *postulation style of reasoning* creates deductively structured theories which include presupposed objects with presupposed properties, and in which the legitimacy of an assertion must be deduced. Thereby, its objects are defined by their suitability for a deductive theory. Hacking mentions six other styles, including the *taxonomic* style, the *statistical* style, and the *algorismic* style. All these styles add to our understanding by employing different ways of saying and determining 'what is', without claiming to describe any reality that would exist independently of them.

It is intriguing that most of the styles described by Crombie (1994) and Hacking (1982) have connections to mathematics. This suggests that mathematics education might be a privileged if not even an imperative place to discuss in school settings how scientific reasoning is possible, even if it does not reveal the properties of any mind-independent reality. It is yet an open question how to approach specific styles in mathematics education and if traditional ways, for example for discussing proof and mathematical modelling in the classroom, are appropriate. However, the rich repertoire of relevant episodes from the history of mathematics and science provided by Crombie (1994), Hacking (1982), and others provides a powerful basis for conceptualising epistemological education through mathematics to face post-factual attitudes.

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D. Kollosche

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